

Deliverable D2.8

Evaluation of the potential legal frameworks for the infrastructure

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1. Executive Summary

The establishment of a joint European genomic data infrastructure requires the establishment of a legal basis under Article 6 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and a legitimisation for processing health and genetic data for the processing within the infrastructure itself as well as for the stakeholders contributing personal data to it or using the personal data. We have identified the challenges related to the the three steps of

- how to bring data into the 1+Million Genomes (1+MG) infrastructure,
- how to disclose data towards users, and
- how to process data as a user, in particular where data use goes beyond research.

Here, together with the 1+MG ELSI Working Group, we have analysed the requirements for and suitability of possible legal instruments for the implementation of the 1+MG infrastructure. Building on the work performed in the Horizon 2020 B1MG project, we have further assessed the potential solutions for their ability to establish a valid legal basis not only for data access provision, but also for data holders and/or data users and their respective processing operations and secondary use purposes. In this document and in alignment with the 1+MG Declaration by the signatory countries, a scenario using a federated data repository, where data remain locally but belong to a joint resource with a joint data governance is considered. The conclusion from the above analysis is that many national legislative frameworks do not provide an adequate solution for all stakeholders.

For data inclusion, not even the European Health Data Space (EHDS) will provide a sufficient legislative framework to achieve the objectives of the 1+MG effectively because it focuses only on data availability through health data access bodies. The reason is that usually a legal basis provided by law only foresees a direct data sharing between a data holder, including permit authorities, and the user. Legislation does not foresee that data are made available within a repository in a harmonised way as envisaged in 1+MG. Where consent is to be used as an alternative, this consent can only be obtained once the 1+MG infrastructure and its governance is established, which in many countries means reconsenting. It also means that data made available through legislation, e.g. as currently the case in genome centres, may not become fully available as not all data subjects will respond to a request to consent or not be available at all if the data holder is a public authority that creates an imbalance between the data subject and the controller. Legitimate interest may only be available where data were not collected based on consent and the data holder is not a public authority.

For lawful data use, the users must be able to rely on a legal basis other than consent because it is not feasible and also not possible in many cases to offer dynamic consent across the entire genome collection of the 1+MG infrastructure. A major hurdle is that the legitimisation for processing health and genetic data in a healthcare reuse context is not defined: legislation usually covers only a direct healthcare professional to patient relationship, not the processing of the data of other patients to

provide care to an own patient. Also in the research context, there can be hurdles as there are no alternatives foreseen to consent as a legal basis for some stakeholders or because there are cumbersome authorisation procedures required.

The legal basis for the data access provision could be established through the mission of the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium, EDIC, which is one of the possible legal instruments evaluated in GDI Pillar I. The EDIC is established through a legal act and as such, a legal act on the Union level could be the basis for the processing for a task in the public interest. However, the Union law establishing 1+MG through an EDIC covers in the first place only the operations of 1+MG itself which are enshrined in its mission (e.g. provide cross-border access to genomes and health data).

It is recommended to explore with the European Commission if the legal coverage can also be extended to the data holders and/or the data users ("European level solution"). An alternative to this approach will require changes on the national level. Such changes, however, may be of interest even beyond 1+MG. It is recommended that all countries review their current legislative framework for the options to support data availability through joint initiatives. The limitations for the legal bases found are not limited to 1+MG but apply in general under all similar situations of alignment for joint interoperable cross-border data resources. Governments should therefore consider a remedy of the situation independent of their participation in, and legal model of 1+MG. The ongoing activities to implement the EU Data Governance Act provide here a unique window of opportunity where the national legislation for secondary use of personal data is addressed already ("National level solution").

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	No

<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

Background for this work

The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)¹ project aims to realise the 1+MG initiative's ambition of creating a data infrastructure that will enable secure access to high quality genomics and corresponding clinical data across Europe. The project involves a consortium of partners from 20 European countries and two infrastructure organisations. It will facilitate a cross-border federated network of national genome collections for biomedical research and personalised medicine.

The Declaration of the 1+MG initiative was signed by all countries in the GDI and aims at a *"supporting data infrastructure to advance research, diseases prevention and personalised health and care"*. The countries agree on cooperating to *"define a governance model of cooperation, particularly concerning the terms and conditions for distributed access to genomic data across borders, usage of the data and other aspects deemed necessary by the signatories"*. The GDI is set out to enable the establishment of a European Genomic Data Infrastructure, further referred to as 1+MG infrastructure.

Establishing an infrastructure requires sustainability and therefore binding commitments by the countries who establish such infrastructure. A governance model means that roles, rights and responsibilities need to be agreed between the countries that provide, maintain and use the infrastructure. Different legal instruments are possible where countries want to commit to a joint endeavour.

Furthermore, the GDPR establishes the requirements for controllers to have a legal basis under the GDPR for the processing of personal data as well as a special legitimation to process health and genetic data. An analysis of the 1+MG ELSI Working Group has revealed that there are legal hurdles to make data available in 1+MG, i.e. the legal transfer from data holders to a principal availability in 1+MG [➤ legal basis for integrating data into the 1+MG infrastructure], as well as for the data users to actually be able to legally access and use the data for their purposes [➤ legal basis for users]. Depending on the legal instrument that will be chosen for implementation, it may also be difficult to establish a legal basis and legitimation to give access to 1+MG data to the users [➤ legal basis for data disclosure to users].

Content of the deliverable

This document provides an overview and an evaluation of advantages and disadvantages of possible options for such legal instruments that may be considered for pan-European infrastructures such as 1+MG. The deliverable also presents potential ways to address the challenges of establishing a legal basis not only for data access provision, but also for data holders and/or data users.

Methodology to produce the deliverable

¹ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

The GDI WP2 Leaders organise monthly meetings with nominated representatives of the 20 countries participating in the GDI project. In these Pillar I (GOV) meetings, the possible legal framework of the future 1+MG infrastructure and legal prerequisites for secondary use were presented and discussed to support the governments' decisions on how to make the genomic data infrastructure legally sustainable.

The input for the Pillar I meetings are derived from work performed in the B1MG project and/or the ELSI Working Group of the 1+MG Initiative. Topics are prepared in smaller groups and then discussed with national ELSI experts nominated by the 1+MG representatives. The ELSI experts also consult with so-called National Mirror Groups, relevant other experts on the national level.

Where relevant, additional external experts are consulted. From the conclusions of the 1+MG ELSI Working Group, documents and recommendations are compiled that provide input to Pillar I to discuss the consequences and suitability of these conclusions and recommendations for the sustainability and legal implementation of the 1+MG initiative.

This document builds on:

- 1) The analysis of possible legal instruments for the sustainable implementation of the 1+MG genomic infrastructure, prepared in collaboration with the 1+MG ELSI Working Group, and first presented to the GDI Pillar I GOV group on 16th December 2022.
- 2) The work of the 1+MG ELSI Working Group on roles under the GDPR for secondary use², on the definition of Purpose and Recital 33 GDPR and on the requirements for a legal basis for the core processing operations, and first presented to the GDI Pillar I GOV group on 27th January 2023.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Legal instrument for the sustainable implementation of the 1+MG genomic infrastructure

4.1.1 Background information

The necessity of countries to find a suitable legal instrument for common undertakings is not new. The European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) was founded in 2002 by the Competitiveness Council as an informal political forum that tries to channel national visions in the field of RI into a common European long term concept. In 2006 a first roadmap of important pan-European research infrastructures was compiled.³ Subsequently, the countries and the

² <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipac011>

³ <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-roadmap>

European Commission were also looking for legal tools to jointly implement pan-European infrastructures and existing options were evaluated for their suitability.

The 1+MG ELSI Working Group was able to build on the exercise performed in the context of research infrastructures and learn from the work that was already done in the past.⁴ However, the situation is different to the ESFRI infrastructures as the scope of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure, to be established through the GDI project and further referred to as 1+MG infrastructure, goes beyond research. The previous analyses also do not include any implications of data protection law.

A workshop by the ELSI Working Group was held in March 2020, which evaluated the tools available at the time. An outcome of the workshop was that all available tools are not optimal for the intended scope of the 1+MG infrastructure. However, the workshop also identified the need to define more precisely the future operations of the 1+MG infrastructure and led to the pursuit of use case workshops, definition of workflows and potential responsibilities in a first draft for a data governance for research use and a legal analysis of the implications of the GDPR on the different principal choices for the legal implementation.

A second workshop was held in April 2022 between representatives of the ELSI Working Group, WP6 of the Beyond 1 Million Genome project (B1MG) including the Coordination Office with project management, communication, governance and sustainability as well as external experts, in which the results of the ELSI Working Group workshop were discussed and in which other infrastructures or initiatives contributed from their experience.

The regular ELSI Working Group meetings were used to analyse the implications of the choice of legal instruments for the roles of the stakeholders under the GDPR and subsequently the consequences for the lawfulness of the processing of personal data in a future 1+MG infrastructure. A document with the result of the analysis was presented on 16 November 2022 in the 1+MG Group meeting. The main result was that creating a legal entity that can be mandated by law is the most suitable solution to provide for the necessary GDPR compliant framework in an efficient way.

4.1.2 Requirements towards the legal instrument for an implementation

Potential candidates as a legal instrument for the implementation of the infrastructure need to be evaluated with respect to their suitability for the intentions and the setup of the planned 1+MG infrastructure. Both legal and practical aspects need to be considered. The following criteria to evaluate the suitability of a legal instrument for the implementation of the 1+MG infrastructure were identified.

⁴ ESFRI, Report of the Workshop on the legal forms of research infrastructures of pan-European interests, 23 March 2006, Brussels; Organised by the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures in collaboration with the European Commission, Directorate General for Research.

- Scope

The instrument must allow for activities that are taking place in the context of research, healthcare and policy development. This is the scope of purposes envisaged in the Declaration and therefore to be covered by the 1+MG infrastructure.

- Membership

- o The instrument must allow countries as members.
- o Membership must not be limited to EU Member States but must at minimum allow members from the European Economic Area (EEA) as Norway as EEA member is already a signatory country to the Declaration.
- o A widening beyond the EEA should ideally be possible to increase the number of accessible genomes and therefore the impact of the 1+MG infrastructure. At minimum the EU Associated Countries⁵ could be considered but the scope of the members decided by the 1+MG Group was considering a potential extension even beyond. This means also third countries beyond the EEA could become members.
- o International organisations or other legal entities (e.g. companies, associations, European Research Infrastructure Consortia, Joint Undertakings) may also be relevant as members.
- o Participation of the European Commission could be an asset for funding (see below).
- o An observer status of countries should be possible.

- Governance

- o A **clearly defined management** of the infrastructure must be established.
- o The setup must allow defined **accountability**, including financial book-keeping.
- o It must be possible to assign roles to different stakeholders, even beyond countries as members (e.g. data holders, data centres / technology contributors, national coordination points, central support).

- Data protection

- o The 1+MG infrastructure must operate within the GDPR legal framework.
- o Controllership roles of the governments should be avoided due to the associated requirements on governments to provide a legal basis and the joint and several liability under the GDPR, which provides a huge risk considering the liability at stake because the processing envisaged in +MG falls under high-risk processing.
- o It must be possible to provide a legal basis under GDPR Art. 6(1) and legitimation under Art. 9(2) for data processing determined jointly by the countries establishing the 1+MG infrastructure, including professional secrecy by law as a safeguard.

⁵ Countries that are associated to the Horizon Europe research framework programme.

- o Ideally, it should also be possible to provide a legal basis for data holders to bring in data to the 1+MG infrastructure for making data available to users in accordance with the jointly agreed data governance.
- Liability
 - o Liability for countries and/or their delegated authorities must be limited.
- Funding
 - o **Instrument must allow a sustainable funding model** for the infrastructure.
 - o Possibility to apply for third party **funding for specific activities undertaken within the 1+MG infrastructure must be possible** [e.g. investments; operations; upgrades].
 - o Ideally it should be possible to tap into EU funds for **setting up** and in particular **running** the infrastructure.
 - o Possibility to gain funds from **data users** (public & private) should be an option.
 - o VAT exemption is often a desired feature.
- Timeframe necessary for establishment
 - o Procedures for setting up the infrastructure must not be too complicated. It should be possible to establish the legal framework within a reasonable timeframe.

4.1.3 Possible legal instruments and evaluation with respect to the criteria

Legal instruments to implement a pan-European infrastructure build on the national and/or European legislation. Different categories of legal frameworks for the implementation were identified by the 1+MG ELSI Working Group. These are the following.

4.1.3.1 Contractual framework (consortium agreement based)⁶

The countries conclude a contract with each other that defines their obligations and rights as well as the functionalities that are fulfilled on the national level to allow the operations of the 1+MG infrastructure. There is no legal entity that incorporates the 1+MG infrastructure. Where services are provided centrally across 1+MG for all countries, these are delegated to one or several already existing legal entities (often members of the consortium).

Example: ELIXIR⁷

Evaluation: A consortium agreement is very flexible. It is agnostic towards the activities that are to be covered and is open towards different members and types of entities to join. This

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Collaborative_partnership

⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance>

flexibility, however, also stretches towards the management and the accountability: a priori, these are not defined; this legal framework does therefore not come with an intrinsic definition of management and accountability. These elements have to be introduced deliberately as part of the agreement. The existence and quality of management and accountability therefore depend on the choices made when negotiating and drafting the agreement. Typically, the responsibilities for management and accountability are delegated to one or several of the members.

The lack of an own legal personality means that all countries through their ministerial representative or, where applicable delegated authority, will become joint controllers for the processing of personal data that is defined through the policies of the 1+MG infrastructure. Consequently, if one or more countries are not from the European Economic Area, their involvement automatically implies a transfer to a third country, i.e. processing no longer subject to the GDPR. Members are jointly and severally liable in this construct.

Sustainability is also not intrinsic but depends on the agreement. It can be more difficult to obtain longer-term commitments from governments where the obligations are only based on a contractual framework.

The possibility to receive EU funds is not entirely excluded but will be more complicated as there is no joint entity to receive funds but the financial contributions would have to go to delegated members and/or be otherwise distributed in the consortium. The VAT exemption will likewise not be defined on the level of the infrastructure but the individual actors.

A contractual agreement is in principle among the frameworks easiest to establish. However, as the agreement is linked to unlimited liability, if possible at all, it may require additional steps on the national level (e.g. involvement of government councils or parliament) to be authorised for signature.

4.1.3.2 Corporate entity based on private law at the national level⁸

A legal personality is created based on an act, typically a registration, which depends on the type of legal person that is created and that is defined in the civil law system in the respective country. Typical examples defined in national legislations are companies (with full or limited liability depending on the choice), associations and economic interest groupings. The conditions that the different entities must adhere to with respect to liability, oversight, tax status etc. are defined in the legislation.

Examples: EOSC⁹, GEANT¹⁰ (Association); XFEL (limited liability company)¹¹

⁸ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Corporation>

⁹ <https://eosc.eu/association>

¹⁰ <https://about.geant.org/our-organisation/>

¹¹ https://www.xfel.eu/organization/partner_countries/index_eng.html

Evaluation: Same as with a consortium agreement above, a corporation can be set up for any purpose. However, being set up under private law, there is no legally assigned mission for the infrastructure's operation. This will cause problems in particular where the 1+MG Infrastructure wants to provide services to support healthcare because any data processing for healthcare must be covered by legislation (unless it can rely on consent). As such, while in principle operations for all purposes are possible from the organisational point of view, it will likely fail the lawfulness criterion for some of them, such as the healthcare related activities that require the national healthcare law to be applicable to the infrastructure to be able to rely on Art. 9.2.h GDPR as well as a legally assigned professional secrecy.

Governments as well as other stakeholders can in principle become members. However, there can be hesitations or even limitations for a government to become member / shareholder under a legal structure in another country and this role may be delegated to another entity mandated by the government. Governmental involvement may therefore be indirect in some cases.

Management and accountability are defined within the legislation of the country. This legislation will also influence the liability and the VAT exemption. For companies, the VAT exemption on member contributions will depend on national legislation.

The corporate entity will become the controller for the personal data processing, which is determined by the members. As long as the chosen host country is within the EU, the entity is operating under the GDPR. The liability (limited vs. unlimited) depends on the chosen form of corporate entity.

This legal framework is likely among the easiest and fastest to set up.

4.1.3.3 Legal entity based on European corporate law: European Economic Interest Grouping (EEIG)¹²

EEIGs are recognised in all European countries. They were created to allow companies or any other entity governed by private or public law to pursue joint (economic) interests.

Example: European Developing Countries Trial Platform (EDCTP1)¹³

Evaluation: With respect to the scope of activities, an EEIG is similar to corporate entities under national law: while in principle, a wide mission can be formed, the legal entity will lack a mandate by law and therefore have problems performing services in support of healthcare.

An EEIG can be formed by companies, firms and other legal entities governed by public or private law which have been formed in accordance with the law of an EU country and which have their registered office in the EU. As such, the extension towards other countries is limited.

¹² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/european-economic-interest-grouping.html>

¹³ <https://www.edctp.org/about-us/the-establishment-of-edctp/#>

The EEIG will act as controller for the operations and will be subject to the GDPR. The management and accountability are clearly defined. Each member has unlimited joint and several liability.

The EEIG does not have an intrinsic sustainability requirement but depends on the setup by its members. It can receive EU funding as well as fees by users for services provided. The entity is subject to national tax laws

4.1.3.4 Intergovernmental organisation based on an international treaty¹⁴

Intergovernmental Organisations are created by international treaties (subject to national ratification procedures), which regulate the mandate and the governance of the Organisation, and have a legal personality under public international law (which is normally also recognised on the domestic level). The level of detailed regulation of the internal working in the establishment treaties varies considerably - and, most of the time, such issues are regulated by internal rules and regulations that need to comply with the establishing treaty. Intergovernmental Organisations enjoy privileges and immunities, which may be provided for in the treaty itself, in separate protocols or in Headquarters/Host Site agreements. The most usual privileges and immunities are immunity from jurisdiction and enforcement, inviolability of premises and archives. Intergovernmental Organisations are not subject to national jurisdiction or oversight and, therefore accountability is a matter regulated internally. This also means that Intergovernmental Organisations are not operating under the GDPR, even if established in the EEA, and any sharing of personal data must be subject to the safeguards of Chapter V GDPR and a data transfer impact assessment.

Only States and, possibly, other Intergovernmental Organisations, can be members of Intergovernmental Organisations, with the criteria of membership, if any, are usually provided for in the establishing treaty.

Example: EMBL¹⁵

Evaluation: An intergovernmental organisation can be set up with any purpose. However, intergovernmental organisations are operating outside the GDPR and any processing of 1+MG health and genomic data or even administrative data from the 1+MG members through the entity or on behalf of the entity are subject to safeguards in Chapter V GDPR. This would lead to a systematic transfer of personal health and genomic data outside the EEA even if the data remain locally. Such solutions are therefore not desirable.

It is open for all countries as members but membership is not available for any other stakeholders. Management and accountability are not predefined and depend on the agreed setup in the treaty. The same accounts for any tax exemptions. Its sustainability also depends

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_organization

¹⁵ <https://www.embl.org/about/>

on the provisions of the treaty. An intergovernmental organisation can receive EU funding and user funds.

Establishment is very laborious, having to go through parliamentary ratification at minimum and is usually chosen only for very large, international undertakings.

4.1.3.5 Legal entities based on Art. 187 TFEU¹⁶

Art. 187 TFEU is the basis for structures that aim at the efficient execution of Union research, technological development and demonstration programmes¹⁷

i. Joint Undertaking¹⁸

Article 187 refers directly to Joint Undertakings (JUs). They are used in particular to set up public-private partnership bodies in order to integrate industrial research in specific areas such as the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI JU) or to forward certain fields relevant for research and development such as high-performance computing with the EuroHPC JU. The decision to set up a JU is taken by the Council following a proposal by the European Commission.

Example: EuroHPC¹⁹

Evaluation: JUs are created through the treaty to support execution of Union research, technological development and demonstration programmes. As such, it does not have a mandate to engage directly in healthcare or policy development. It is therefore unlikely that a regulation setting up the JU could provide it with the necessary lawful basis under the GDPR.

Membership includes typically the European Commission and it allows public and private bodies. However, countries other than countries associated to the EU research and development programmes are difficult to include.

The controllership for processing of personal data is with the JU as a legal entity. As a Union body, a JU is not subject to the GDPR but the Regulation 2018/1725²⁰, which is aligned with the GDPR and therefore offers equivalent protection.

¹⁶ The Union may set up joint undertakings or any other structure necessary for the efficient execution of Union research, technological development and demonstration programmes.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A12016E187>

¹⁷ The analysis is limited to Art. 187 TFEU structures. Art. 185 TFEU also allows joint activities of the Union and the Member States but these are not related to any structure that has a legal personality. Therefore, the other considerations to the listed options with respect to advantages and disadvantages will apply as one of these options would have to be chosen.

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/joint-undertakings.html>

¹⁹ https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/about/discover-eurohpc-ju_en

²⁰ Regulation 2018/1725 sets forth the rules applicable to the processing of personal data by European Union institutions, bodies, offices and agencies. It is aligned with the General Data Protection Regulation and the Data Protection Law Enforcement Directive. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1552577087456&uri=CELEX:32018R1725>

While JUs are being set up in a sustainable fashion, their duration is linked to the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF)²¹ of the EU and needs to be reconfirmed with each new framework. The budget of a JU is usually defined on the level of the council regulation, which specifies the EU funds and the contributions by the partners in the JU. JUs are predominantly set up as funding programmes to stimulate certain sectors rather than to design and operate directly an infrastructure such as in the 1+MG case. There is no limitation of liability for JU.

Setting up a JU requires approval through the Council.

ii. European Research Infrastructure Consortium²²

JUs focus mainly on joint funding programmes, which proved to be not enough when the countries decided to establish pan-European research infrastructures. Building on the option to also create other structures, the possibility to create European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs) was enabled through Regulation (EC) No 723/2009.²³ This was a direct response to the analyses in the context of the ESFRI activities where it was concluded that none of the existing legal instruments at the time seemed well suited for the intended aim to facilitate the establishment and the operation of research infrastructures with European interest among several EU countries and associated countries. ERICs have a legal personality and full legal capacity recognised in all EU countries. The basic internal structure of an ERIC is flexible and defined in its statutes by its members. They are being set up through a Commission Implementing Decision.

Example: BBMRI-ERIC²⁴

Evaluation: ERICs were set up to provide a tool to facilitate the setting up and operation of research infrastructures. Therefore, the scope of activities of an ERIC is limited to research related activities and it cannot be used to facilitate other infrastructures beyond research. Correspondingly, the legal act to establish them cannot be used to provide a legal basis for processing of personal data that is not related to research purposes or the operations of a research infrastructure.

Membership is possible for EU Member States, countries associated to the research framework programme of the EU, third countries and intergovernmental organisations. The non-EU countries and intergovernmental organisations have to recognise the legal personality and capacity of an ERIC in their own legislative framework. Other stakeholders as members are not foreseen. EU Member States must be in the majority in the consortium.

²¹ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/29/multiannual-financial-framework>

²² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM:ri0005>

²³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/AUTO/?uri=celex:02009R0723-20131226>

²⁴ <https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/about/>

The regulation establishing the ERIC as a legal instrument makes provision for the management and accountability that an ERIC has to adhere to. As an entity with its own legal personality, the ERIC acts as controller for the processing.

Liability is either unlimited or limited to the contribution of the members unless otherwise foreseen in the statutes. It is a precondition for founding an ERIC that sustainability is ensured by the members. ERICs can receive EU funding as well as income from users. It is a condition for the establishment of an ERIC that the host country grants a status as an international organisation with an exemption from VAT.

Setting up an ERIC is fairly straight-forward based on the statutes but additional time for a few months needs to be considered for the Commission Implementation Decision that exhibits the legal act for the establishment. However, in terms of an establishment through a legal act, this procedure is probably the fastest possible as it has a clearly defined timeframe of a few months for the Commission Implementing Decision and does not depend on the ratification in parliament or the Council, which is always more difficult to predict.

4.1.3.6 European Digital Infrastructure Consortium²⁵

The Decision of the European Parliament and of the Council on the “Path to the Digital Decade” provides an overview of legal options that multi-country projects can pursue. It also introduces the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC) as a new legal structure. The EDIC is similar to the ERIC in the overall setup and equally established through a Commission Implementing Decision but has more flexibility with regard to membership and purpose.

Evaluation: The EDIC legal instrument was inspired by ERIC and is similar in many aspects, but comes with additional options and more flexibility. Most relevant for 1+MG is that an EDIC can pursue all purposes that are relevant for the digital agenda. It can therefore also cover healthcare and policy development. The EDIC aims to allow multi-country projects to pool EU, national and private resources to support the digital transformation of the Union. As such, the mission of an EDIC can cover all operations that may be needed in data spaces, which form a major goal in the realisation of the EU Strategy for Data. The establishment of an EDIC through a Commission Implementing Decision can therefore provide the legal basis for data processing necessary for the EDIC to pursue its mission.

Membership in an EDIC is rather open: while the application must be done by at least 3 EU Member States, other entities can be members. These may include among others third countries, international organisations and private bodies under the prerequisite that the EU Member States hold the majority of voting rights. Same as for the ERIC, it is required that the third countries and international organisations recognise in their legislative framework the legal capacity of the EDIC. Although the Commission cannot become a member of an EDIC, it

²⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0574>

will be allowed to participate in the decision-making body as a non-voting member. It may veto decisions by the decision-making body in case it provides funding to the infrastructure.

Otherwise the setup is very similar to the ERIC: management and accountability will be provided for in the "Path to the Digital Decade" Decision. The EDIC can act as controller and is subject to the GDPR. The liability is limited unless otherwise stated in the statutes. The members must provide for the sustainability and the EDIC is created for an open-ended timeframe. It can receive EU funds as well as fees from users. The VAT exemption is given through the recognition in the host country as an international organisation; however, in case of the EDIC, this is optional rather than obligatory and may not apply where private companies join as members.

The setting up through a Commission Implementation Decision is again the most straightforward way to provide a legal entity for the 1+MG Infrastructure. Most importantly, it would come with a legal basis for the processing of personal health and genetic data under the GDPR.

4.1.3.7 Overview of the evaluation of instruments and their suitability

Overview table: Evaluation of instruments for their suitability

✓ : YES (✓): depends on choices made ~ : not entirely ✗ : NO

	Consortium agreement	Corporate entity on national law	EEIG	Intergov. Organisation	Joint Undertaking	ERIC	EDIC
Suitable for research, healthcare and policy development purposes	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓ ⁺ / ✗ ⁺	✓ ⁺
Possibility to create lawfulness under Art. 6.1.e/9.2 including professional secrecy	✗	✗	✗	n/a**	✓ [*] / ✗ ⁺	✓ [*] / ✗ ⁺	✓
Open for non-EU countries as members	✓	✓	~	✓	✓	✓	✓
Open for other stakeholders as members	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓
Clearly defined management and accountability	(✓)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Operating inside GDPR	(✓)	(✓)	✓	✗	~/✓	✓	✓
Controllership with 1+MG infrastructure	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Limited liability	✗	(✓)	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓
Sustainability	(✓)	(✓)	(✓)	✓	✓	✓	✓
Possibility to receive community funds	(✓)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Possibility to receive user funds	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

VAT exemption	(✓)	~	✗	✓	✓	✓	(✓)
Reasonably easy and fast to establish	(✓)	✓	✓	✗	~	✓	✓

*: research only; ⁺: healthcare and policy development; **: operates outside GDPR; [†]: subject to Commission Implementing Decision

4.2 GDPR challenges for data transfers in 1+MG

4.2.1 GDPR background and national implementation

Under the GDPR, the entity that determines the purposes and the essential means, is the controller for this processing. This entity decides why and how the processing is performed. Crucially, the controllership is not affected by where the data are processed or by whom. It is also not decisive what precise collection of data is processed. Rather, deciding on the selection criteria determining how the data are chosen – which corresponds, for example, to the inclusion criteria for research subjects in a scientific research project – is associated with controllership.

The controller is responsible for the compliance of the processing with the fundamental data protection principles of the GDPR (Art. 5), most pertinently, the principles of lawfulness, fairness and transparency, purpose limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity and confidentiality. The controller is also accountable for being able to demonstrate such compliance (the principle of accountability).

To fulfil the requirement of lawfulness of processing, a controller must have a legal basis under the Art. 6 of the GDPR. For the secondary use purposes, the relevant legal grounds are

- Consent by the data subject to one or more specific purposes (Art. 6.1.a), this consent must be freely given, there must not be an imbalance between the data subject and the controller and the consent must be informed.
- Legal obligation (Art. 6.1.c) can be applicable to make data principally available for secondary use where this is established by law, such as for data holders in the Proposal for a Regulation on the European Health Data Space.
- Task in the public interest where such task is defined in a law to which the controller is subject (Art. 6.1.e) and
- Legitimate interest of the controller or a third party (Art. 6.1.f) for which an interest needs to be real and present, and a balancing exercise has to be performed to ascertain that the interest of the controller or third party outweighs the interests of the data subject. This legal basis is not available to public authorities that have collected the data in the performance of their tasks.

In addition to the legal basis itself, the controller also needs a legitimization if special categories of data are being processed, as required under Art. 9(2) GDPR. In the context of secondary use, possible Art. 9(2) GDPR conditions include the following:

- the explicit consent of the data subject (Art. 9.2.a),
- processing based on Union or Member State law that also foresees specific safeguards for the processing; the options depend on the purposes of the processing
 - processing is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest (Art. 9.2.g)
 - processing is necessary in a healthcare context where the controller is subject to an obligation of secrecy under Union or Member State law or rules established by national competent bodies (Art. 9.2.h)
 - processing is necessary for scientific research purposes (Art. 9.2.j)

Member States have the possibility to introduce limitations and additional conditions on the processing of health and genetic data based on Art. 9.4 GDPR. As one implementation of this legislative option, some countries require consent as a legal basis for the processing of health and genetic data, and/or mandate that a specific derogation be obtained from a competent body for research purposes. There are also countries where Art. 9.2 legitimations have not been introduced for all stakeholders (e.g. excluding private actors) or are not covering all activities (e.g. regulating processing of data for healthcare only for the patient data by the treating healthcare professionals).

The requirements for the legal basis consent to be specific and informed mean that the consent must be given to individual purposes (Recital 32) and the identity of the controller must be known to the data subject (Recital 42). While Recital 33 states that consent may be given to areas of research, this is not generally accessible according to our findings. Such a less specific approach will only be possible for primary processing that cannot be fully identified at the time of collection, i.e. before the processing starts. Where data are further processed by the controller, it is assumed that it is possible to obtain a consent once the purpose for the further processing is fully defined and that there is no need to compromise on the specificity of consent. Considering that a Recital can only provide an interpretation of the legislation but not derogate from it, a consenting to future rather undefined purposes, which do not influence the collection, will go beyond a mere interpretation of what covers consenting to specific purposes. Indeed, some countries explicitly foresee that further processing of health and genetic data requires a separate consent (e.g., Cyprus, Ireland) or a special authorisation by the Supervisory Authority (e.g., Italy). The approach of Nordic countries on the other hand is to create a legal framework for secondary use that provides avenues that make consent as potential legal basis for the secondary use obsolete (e.g., Denmark, Finland, Sweden, Norway).

4.2.2 Main processing operations and secondary use purposes when involving a repository and legal consequences for the processing

The main purposes along the processing chain when sharing data through a repository are as follows (see Picture 1):

➤ **Making data available through a repository as interoperable data with a defined data governance**

(includes the data curation into required data models; characterisation of data with metadata; legal transfer to the repository, potentially also physical transfer to a repository)

➤ **Contributing data to the user's specific purpose**

(includes data selection in compliance with the data minimisation principle, and data disclosure to the user)

➤ **Processing for the user's purposes**

(data use depends on the purposes of the users; it can include data discovery, data cleaning, data linkage and integration, data analysis, data archiving, etc. in a research context or be more limited to data queries in healthcare)

Picture 1: Purposes along the processing chain of secondary use through a repository.

The collection context falls outside secondary use and is therefore not discussed. However, depending on where data are collected, this influences the restrictions on secondary use: healthcare data fall under medical secrecy; data collected by public authorities can only be made available for secondary use based on a legal mandate.

The legal consequences for the processing for each operation are as follows:

➤ **Making data available through a repository**

The legal analysis has revealed that it is in general not easy to make data broadly available as harmonised datasets across different collections and according to a harmonised governance. Where data is made available based on consent, the modalities of how data will be made available (data governance) must be part of the consent for consent to be informed. As the data are typically collected for a certain purpose and secondary use exhibits further processing, the necessity for specificity of consent applies. With a view on existing datasets, this means the envisaged repository must already be known or reconsenting is required later on before the transfer.

However, consent is not suitable for all collection situations, such as where there is an imbalance between the data subject and the controller. That is particularly relevant in healthcare.

Where data are made available through legislation, the legislation defines the data governance, which does not foresee the data provision through a harmonised governance in a pan-European federated repository such as in the 1+MG infrastructure. In our view, new legislation will be needed to overcome this problem. In the current legislative proposal, even the EHDS Regulation will not solve the challenge because it also defines only the direct data governance from data holder to data user. It does not provide the legal basis for creating an alignment across different collections with the aim to harmonise datasets and to offer an efficient and harmonised data governance across different sources of data collections.

Special attention has also to be given to the fact that making personal data available for secondary use purposes constitutes further processing. Whereas research use can be considered as compatible further processing, for other purposes a compatibility test is needed.

While legitimate interest can provide a legal basis for making data available as well, it needs to be noticed that data collected based on consent as legal basis is difficult to further process based on a different legal basis as it is often perceived as unfair. A data protection impact assessment with prior consultation of the data protection authorities would be required. It is also to be noted that public authorities cannot use legitimate interest at all. This may include genome centres and even universities, hospitals and public research centres.

The problem of not being able to make data available through jointly agreed standards on a wider national or European level constitutes a fundamental challenge of a general nature. This limitation will hamper the prospects of cross-border availability of larger high-value datasets in Europe. It also means that data remain with individual data holders, such as healthcare providers, with often inadequate resources to provide data governance and data management for secondary use, whereas legally established dedicated repositories with sufficient resources could provide a more reliable and efficient data governance.

➤ **Contributing data to the user's purposes**

Only a few countries have legislation in place that provides for secondary use of data through independent users. A legally established mandate to make data available to user's purposes is often only established for public authorities in the pursuit of their tasks. Also, in healthcare it is sometimes defined in the national or regional legislative framework how these could be made available for users in a different context.

In many cases the secondary use of users' own purposes is limited to research activities. In rare cases, policy development is considered or, in case of a healthcare context, a healthcare reuse of data for the diagnosis and treatment of other patients. Education is another potential field of secondary use. Where purposes, such as policy development, are missing in the legislation, the avenue to these purposes is closed. The only option left is a specific consent, but this may be ruled out due to imbalance between data subject and controller. Consent would also have to be given to each data sharing for a different purpose ("dynamic consent"). As e.g., each research project and each

policy aim constitutes a new purpose, the consent approach does not scale for data space solutions. No other legal basis is available to a public authority than as a legitimate interest for data acquired as part of the performance of the tasks is ruled out.

Most entities who collected data in a research context or otherwise related to their primary mission will not have a mission for making data available to others outside their own pursuit of tasks. Therefore, they are subject to the same problems as described above. An alternative open might be to rely on legitimate interest. However, this is only possible where it is not precluded by a status as public authority and not seen as an unfair processing, e.g., in case data were collected under consent as a legal basis when performing the required balancing test.

There is a further challenge of sharing special categories of data for purposes like healthcare reuse or potentially even policy development where there is a legal requirement for the controller to operate under professional secrecy established following Art. 9.2.h / Art. 9.2.i GDPR in combination with Art. 9.3 GDPR. Such professional secrecy must be established by law or rules established by national competent bodies. This, however, does not seem applicable as the processing is exactly about not keeping secrecy but sharing with users. Therefore, alternative legitimations should be envisaged and/or the possibility of alternative safeguards as it is also practice in the healthcare context when relieving from medical secrecy to be able to use data for research or quality measures.

Legislation like the EHDS Regulation will foresee the legal basis to make data available for secondary use but this will only be possible through the defined framework of the EHDS. The EHDS Regulation will not provide a principal mandate to share data, e.g. for non-health related purposes such as socio-economic research or outside the EHDS framework. It will also not establish a legal basis for the data sharing by stakeholders other than data holders or Health Data Access Bodies in the context of and according to the data governance of the EHDS. 1+MG as data infrastructure must establish its own legal basis and related data governance and safeguards.

➤ **Processing for the user's purposes**

Users pursue the processing of personal data for their purposes as sole controllers and under their own national data protection legislation. The analysis of the legal landscape in Europe has resulted in the conclusion that not all users have a valid legal basis available for secondary use of personal data for research, healthcare or policy development outside consent or must undergo burdensome procedures whereby they can be exempted from obtaining consent. Consent, as already elaborated above, would only be valid where it is implemented as a dynamic consent, allowing for a specific consent for each user and user's purpose. Such a solution, however, will not scale to a data space of regular reuse, which would require almost constant feedback by the data subjects. In addition, consent may not even be a valid legal basis where the purposes of the user do not allow data to be withdrawn mid-processing. The most straight-forward solution for users is to build on their mission when pursuing the processing, which will allow in principle the choice of legitimate interest or task in the public interest as a legal basis under Art. 6.1 GDPR.

The situation becomes more challenging where special categories of data are processed as is the case in 1+MG. In several countries there are serious limitations of the options to actually allow the user to establish a valid legitimization under Art. 9.2 GDPR. Often consent is required as a legal basis based on Art. 6.4 GDPR and deviations from consent, if possible at all, require specific authorisations. It may also be that the exemption under Art. 9.2 GDPR was not implemented at all for a certain stakeholder group such as private entities and/or a group of purposes such as data reuse in healthcare, which then provides a similar hurdle. This latter scenario applies in particular to healthcare professionals where the legislation often addresses only the direct relationship to the patient but not the use of data from other patients to enable the diagnosis and treatment of an own patient.

4.2.3 Potential solutions for establishing a valid legal basis for all main processing operations and secondary use purposes

We have identified two potential ways to address this challenge:

- i. One option will be to explore with the European Commission if it is to assign a task in the public interest to both data holders and users when they contribute to the objectives of the 1+MG EDIC (> European level solution).
- ii. The other option is that each country will address the current gaps in their legislation during the currently ongoing legislative measures in the context of the implementation of the Data Governance Act (DGA) on the national level. This is a window of opportunity open only in the year 2023. (> National level solution)

> i. Solution on the European level (EDIC based)

The considerations start with the role of an European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC) as the legal implementation of the pan-European infrastructure. The implementation of the currently envisaged model of the data governance for the access decision means that the legal entity of the 1+MG infrastructure takes controllership for the data access decision. Where such a legal entity is established through a legislative act, it means that it receives its mission through this act.²⁶

Where a processing of special categories of data is necessary for a task or mission foreseen by law, that law also provides for a legitimization under Art. 9.2 with the corresponding safeguards. In case of the 1+MG EDIC, this would be the case through the data governance and the related data protection by design and default implementation and can also include an assignment of professional secrecy to the EDIC and its employees.

²⁶ See e.g., EDPB Opinion 03/2019: "The processing of personal data in the context of clinical trials can thus be considered as necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest when the conduct of clinical trials directly falls within the mandate, missions and tasks vested in a public or private body by national law."

An EDIC is created through a Commission Implementing Decision. While such Decision is only based on a delegated procedure, it nevertheless has binding character and is directly applicable without transposition into national law. Recital 41 GDPR confirms that where the GDPR "refers to a legal basis or a legislative measure, this does not necessarily require a legislative act adopted by a parliament". This suggests that delegated acts are sufficient: where the Commission has the mandate to establish EDICs for implementing Multi-Country Projects around data infrastructure, then the processing of the data could be covered by that Decision to the extent that the mission of the specific EDIC as a multi-country project is part of the legislative act. It could then be possible to establish the necessary legal framework under the GDPR for the data access provision through the assignment of the mission of the 1+MG EDIC to provide access to genomic and health data for the purposes defined in the Declaration.²⁷

A more challenging question is if the legislative act establishing the EDIC can also establish a legal basis for other entities than the EDIC itself. Looking into Recital 45 GDPR, it is stated "[...]where processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority, the processing should have a basis in Union or Member State law. [...] It should also be for Union or Member State law to determine whether the controller performing a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority should be a public authority or another natural or legal person governed by public law, or, where it is in the public interest to do so, including for health purposes such as public health and social protection and the management of health care services, by private law, such as a professional association." This statement suggests that a legislative act can provide a legal assignment of a task or a mission not only to an entity established by that law but in principle to any person. This is further supported by Recital 41 GDPR that says as long as this assignment is sufficiently clear: "[...] such a legal basis or legislative measure should be clear and precise and its application should be foreseeable to persons subject to it".

Based on these considerations, the 1+MG Initiative as such is reviewed. The core mission statement of the declaration, written in bold, is:

"In order to realise this shared vision, the signatories of this declaration agree to work together to provide cross-border, data-driven health and care solutions to benefit citizens of the Union. As part of this goal the signatories will work towards building a research cohort of at least 1 million sequenced genomes accessible in the EU by 2022. This cooperation, which will build upon existing initiatives in genomics and personalised medicine, will inter alia aim to [...]" The subsequent implementation considerations refer to interoperability, secure processing environments, cooperative governance and compliance with the GDPR.

From this mission statement, we can derive:

1. Data are not to be generated through the 1+MG initiative but should be available from genome initiatives.

²⁷ Declaration 'Towards access to at least 1 million sequenced genomes in the EU by 2022', https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=50964

2. The major aim is to make these data accessible for secondary use.

The Declaration has been signed to make this availability possible in a GDPR compliant way. Art. 13 DDPP suggests that an EDIC is a tool to implement a Multi-Country Project.²⁸ This can be interpreted that an EDIC is more than merely establishing an infrastructure but rather about realising the wider objective of the Multi-Country project and to which the infrastructure itself contributes. Then it can be argued that the wider objective of the Multi-Country Project should be covered by the legislative act as well. In this case it means that a task for making genomic data available is assigned to data holders in the countries participating in the Multi-Country Project. The data governance for data inclusion hereby defines which data holders and which data is covered by 1+MG and what the necessary safeguards are that need to be fulfilled for GDPR compliance and to make the data lawfully available in the 1+MG federated infrastructure.

Such an approach of not only covering the actual data sharing but also the step to make data available reflects the common practice of how registries or repositories are being set up. The legislation always includes two elements: how are data being made available and how is access provided to users. This is equally reflected for example in the EHDS Regulation where the availability through data holders is defined as well as the conditions how Health Data Access Bodies give access to users.

An ultimate goal of the 1+MG Declaration is to achieve better health: *“Develop a coordinated data governance framework necessary to facilitate Europe-wide large-scale processing of health and related data in compliance with the applicable data protection legal framework, in order to support shared health policy goals; notably to achieve better health for citizens, future sustainability of health systems, and to boost large-scale data-driven biomedical and clinical R&D in Europe”*. This goal of 1+MG can only be achieved through the users that produce results from the data use that leads to input into prevention, healthcare and better healthcare systems. It is therefore worth considering that a task in the public interest could be assigned to users who use the data of 1+MG to contribute to the ultimate goals of 1+MG and comply with the safeguards defined in 1+MG's data governance. Following the suggestions of the Recitals 41 and 45 GDPR, a task to contribute 1+MG's goal can clearly be assigned to defined persons. The data governance fulfils hereby the aspects referred to in Art. 6.3 GDPR: *“That legal basis may contain specific provisions to adapt the application of rules of this Regulation, inter alia: the general conditions governing the lawfulness of processing by the controller; the types of data which are subject to the processing; the data subjects concerned; the entities to, and the purposes for which, the personal data may be disclosed; the purpose limitation; storage periods; and processing operations and processing procedures, including measures to ensure lawful and fair processing such as those for other specific processing situations as provided for in Chapter IX”*. It would also provide the safeguards required in Arts. 9.2.g/h/i/j GDPR.

²⁸ Decision (EU) 2022/2481 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 establishing the Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030. “Article 13 Objective and status of EDICs. 1. Member States may implement a multi-country project by means of an EDIC.”

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022D2481&qid=1671519436597>

➤ ii. **Solution on the national level (national legislation based)**

There is a unique chance to remedy the observed limitations when it comes to data availability for secondary use and the data use itself as all countries in the EEA are now working on the legal implementation of the EU Data Governance Act (DGA), which requires among other things the establishment of certain structures and the designation of such as competent bodies and competent authorities. The national legislation may take a wider scope and address also general questions of data availability for secondary use. Such legislative measures could build in a clause that provides a legal basis for data holders to make data available for reuse through dedicated public sector bodies. These public sector bodies may be required to have a clear legal competence to grant or refuse access under national or Union law for defined purposes of public interest, with their data reuse conditions satisfying the requirements set out in Art. 5(2)-(11) DGA whenever the reuse is regulated in national law. This would allow transfers to repositories, at least where such repositories are established through a Union or Member State legal act. It could also be considered to allow transfers to repositories that fulfil certain requirements but are not individually established by law. Overall, such a clause would lead to the possibility of participating in more joint efforts towards harmonisation of data and could result in more well-administered data collections. It would also allow research stakeholders to fulfil the expectation of public funders to make their data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR data) after the finalisation of the project. They could transfer this responsibility to a well administered repository rather than having to provide all the infrastructure and expertise to manage the data access themselves. Such possibility will boost data availability and thus the potential of an increased value creation from data.

The legislative changes based on the DGA implementation in the EU Member States could also be used to unlock data that are currently confined by a lack of a legal basis on the side of controllers who collected the data to share these data with independent users. Widening of the scope of secondary use from research to other purposes in the public interest, such as clinical reuse of one patient's data for the benefit of another, should be considered including corresponding suitable safeguards to ensure the fairness towards the data subjects. Safeguards when extending the scope of secondary use purposes should e.g. include a proactive communication with a clear and easy opt-out mechanism for both, the principal widening of data reuse as well as, where applicable, individual data disclosures.

Additionally, the DGA will foster the altruistic sharing of data which may unlock further data for research. It does so by mandating work on a European form for consent, which could provide more clarity around the notion of "broad consent" and "dynamic consent", and creating a label for data altruism organisations that should serve as an intermediary between individuals giving consent on one side and researchers on the other. However, it will not solve the challenges of consent as a legal basis as indicated above and will not help to unlock the population-level data from the public sector. It will also always be related to a selection bias because the data subjects willing to share their data actively are not representative of the population.

The DGA implementation can also be an opportunity to reconsider the legal implementation of Art. 9.2 GDPR and fill gaps where the legitimation to process special categories of data has been

insufficiently implemented, not covering all possible stakeholders or processing scenarios. Also restrictions to use consent when processing health and/or genetic data could be lifted where the processing takes place in the controlled environment of a repository overseen by law. Countries that have not implemented the full scope of options under Art. 9.2 to support the improvement of personalised medicine therefore may want to enable their national stakeholders to lawfully reuse special categories of data in research, healthcare and policy development, at minimum where such processing takes place within repositories that are satisfying the requirements set out in Art. 5 DGA.

Once the EHDS infrastructure HealthData@EU is in place, the EHDS Regulation may provide for the Art. 9.2 GDPR legitimation for the users of 1+MG federated infrastructure. However, the consequences of an integration of data infrastructures as "authorised participants" is currently not clear and the EHDS Regulation proposal is still under development.

5. Conclusion

It was proposed to focus the legal implementation planning for the 1+MG genomic infrastructure on the European Digital Infrastructure Consortium, EDIC, as an instrument because it is the only instrument that offers the possibility to provide a legal framework for all envisaged purposes of the 1+MG infrastructure. Many existing tools like the ERICs are established in the research context only. Other tools are flexible enough but would require additional legislation to provide the necessary exemption under Art. 9.2 GDPR to process health and genetic data.

A tabular summary of the analysis of different legal instruments that might be considered is provided in section 4.1.3.7. With a decision to move forward with the EDIC, efforts can be concentrated on a single legal instrument as otherwise progress will be hard to achieve if several legal situations would have to be pursued in parallel. Nevertheless, should the EDIC turn out to be non-satisfactory, the 1+MG Group could still revert to exploring alternative models.

The EDIC as a legal instrument would allow also to explore the possibilities to provide a legal basis for data holders and/or data users. In several countries, this will otherwise require a change of national legislation to unlock genome data for 1+MG infrastructure or to enable all users to have access. The EDIC appears to reflect the need for infrastructures in European data spaces. As such it seems to fit best the needs of the 1+MG infrastructure.

On 24th February 2023, the GDI Pillar I GOV group concluded that the EDIC is the legal instrument to focus our efforts on and unanimously recommended to move forward with the EDIC as the potential solution for the 1+MG infrastructure. This recommendation was proposed to and endorsed by the 1+MG Group meeting on 31st March 2023. So far, 19 countries have now signed an expression of interest in a call by the European Commission to implement the 1+MG infrastructure through an EDIC. In another call by the Commission for a pre-notification, i.e., a reinforced interest declaration with additional financial information, so far 9 countries have signed.

6. Next steps

Following the decision to focus on the EDIC as the potential solution, GDI WP2 will next look into the EDIC with respect to:

- If / How the Commission Implementing Decision can provide a legal basis for the operations of the 1+MG infrastructure;
- How to project our considerations on the structure of the statutes of the future 1+MG infrastructure;
- What content needs to be regulated and in what way; and
- If / How the EDIC legal act can potentially be used for establishing a legal basis for the processing for the various purposes as described above.

GDI WP2 will follow up with the European Commission regarding the possibility of covering a legal basis for the processing of and for providing solutions to data holders and/or data users.

